

Classroom Management Competence of Senior High School Teachers in Anda, Division of Pangasinan I

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Abstract

This descriptive-comparative study explored the factors influencing college students' participation in physical fitness activities at an autonomous university in a highly urbanized city in Central Philippines during the 2025–2026 school year. A total of 342 first-year students were surveyed using a validated questionnaire, and the data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and the Mann-Whitney U test. The results revealed that students value the physical, emotional, social, and mental benefits of fitness, yet heavy academic workloads, inadequate facilities, and time constraints often limit their participation. Significant differences were found when grouped by course and sex. Non-board program students reported higher engagement than board program students, suggesting that lighter academic demands allow greater flexibility for physical activity. Male students also showed greater participation than females, reflecting broader social and cultural influences, as well as differences in motivation and opportunity. Ultimately, the research provides a framework for designing a holistic fitness program that balances academic responsibilities with student well-being, ensuring that physical activity becomes a consistent and meaningful part of college life. The proposed intervention integrates safe routines, emotional rewards, peer support, and mindfulness to sustain engagement.

Keywords: *Classroom Management Competence, Managing the Learning Environment, Managing Relationships, Managing Learners, Managing Resources*

I. THE PROBLEM

Rationale

Senior High School Classroom Management particularly in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) is one of the major responsibilities of teachers. The central purpose of every track in senior high school is to establish and maintain a learning environment that fosters both effective and efficient instruction while maintaining a positive social culture for learners. The teachers as a classroom manager is the main factor involved for learners' progress academically, culturally, morally and spiritually. They should be patient enough and have a wide understanding for learner's individual differences. For this, an effective teacher should make provisions for accomplishing classroom tasks and activities before classes begin Evertson, (2022).

Ornstein (2021) identified classroom management as a primary recipe for an effective teaching and learning encounter. Better and more effective and efficient classroom management promotes a healthy learning environment. Furthermore, according to him, classroom management is the main concern of teachers every day. It plays a crucial role in the teaching-learning process. The effectiveness of classroom management hinges primarily on the teacher as a classroom manager. The teacher acts as a facilitator of learning. He cannot perform his role as such, if he cannot control the class. The teacher, as a classroom manager, should be able to handle the different types of learners. No matter how much potential the teacher has, if he is unable to manage the learners in the classroom, little learning will take place.

The teacher, being a facilitator is someone who draws out the abilities and potentials of his learners. He has to establish standards and coordinating work procedures. It suggests that the role of teachers is to help learners understand and identify the task to be performed.

According to Cooper (2023), the intent of facilitative management behavior is the improvement of the classroom conditions that promote effective instruction. The teacher is a facilitator of learning. A good classroom atmosphere that is conducive for learning is also to be paid attention by the teacher. An effective classroom management establishes the conditions that enable the learners to be productive. The maintenance task of the teacher is to sustain level of interest among the learners, establish positive interpersonal relationship among the learners and to build effective communication.

A well-managed class is conducive to mental growth and development learning becomes interesting and enjoyable under favorable conditions.

Sebald (2023), stressed that in a disciplined classroom, the learners develop independence and responsibility. A teacher can be a better classroom manager by utilizing varied classroom management approaches that promote learner's development along discipline, cooperative learning and social relationships.

Classroom management is one of the main concerns of teachers, administrators, and parents. If the school is to live up to the community's expectation that it is a learning-productive enterprise, the individual classrooms which comprise the school must contribute to the school's educational productivity. Learning is the central goal of the total school operation, and teaching

is the school's basic production technique. Effective teaching and effective learning take place in well-managed classrooms. When class time is consumed by management problems, learners are the losers, for little real learning takes place. As pointed out by Good (1979), a good classroom management is one of the strongest influences on academic learning.

Classroom management refers to operational and control of activities involving details as seating arrangement, attendance, utilization of instructional materials and facilities, classroom courtesies and discipline and other forms of learning environment which requires foresight and planning (Lardizabal, 2023).

On the other hand, according to Bilbao (2023) classroom management refers to the variety of skills and techniques that teachers use to keep learners organized, orderly focused and attentive on their tasks primarily to ensure an effective teaching–learning process.

Effective classroom management can promote an atmosphere of interactive–cooperative learning thereby improving learners' academic performance including their rational moralism. Likewise, it can contribute to increase teacher's performance. Teacher's performance has become a major issue in current movements of educational reform and school improvement. No matter which move of reform we are riding on, it is generally agreed that teacher is the key element for success of school education (Calderon, 2022).

In the local setting, based on the personal observations, feedbacks and utmost from the experiences of the researcher, classroom management if not properly handled, can provide adverse effect to classroom environment as evidenced by learners who are noisy, not listening to their teachers, fond of bullying, always going out while discussion is going, shouting inside the classroom and other unnecessary activities. These may affect their academic performances.

The ability to manage a classroom in an efficient and effective manner is a valued mark of a competent teacher. The test to qualify for a “badge of meritorious performance” includes consistent behavior and action indicative of complete control, direction and guidance of all teaching learning activities. There is also a felt-need to consider the needs of the learners by way of employing effective instructional methodologies and appropriate learning materials as well as dealing with learners' varied interest and abilities can promote a facilitative atmosphere for learning.

Along this context, classroom management has generally four (4) major competencies. These are: Managing the Learning Environment, Managing Relationship, Managing Learners and Managing Resources.

Managing the Learning Environment refers to a dimension of classroom management competency which is associated with conduciveness and setting up classroom environment based on learning needs and interest of learners. This means a sound and healthy learning environment should adhere to the true to life experience, needs and other learning backgrounds of the learners to make learning more meaningful permanent and effective. Managing Relationship refers to establishing exemplary and concordant relationship with the learners. This is done by way of establishing report, encouraging and inspiring them in all matters which can contribute to a better and meaningful learning perspectives. Managing Learners refers to the act or art of controlling learners' behavior and other expectations and roles that emanate in the classroom. This is done

by way of transpiring or transmitting comprehensive knowledge skills and helping them to improve and rectify proper values as to make them productive and responsible citizens of the society. Managing Resources refers to employing techniques and strategies for effective and efficient teaching, designing tasks to be carried out including proper and maximum utilization of resources. This also concerns with how to manage time efficiently and effectively which is also the concern of a teacher in his/her classroom management.

The importance of having a well-managed classroom contribute to an effective classroom environment thereby ensuring an atmosphere of lively and prolific teaching-learning endeavors. It can establish the conditions that enable the learners to be productive likewise, conducive to mental growth including development learning which becomes interesting and enjoyable under favorable conditions. Further, it facilitates social and emotional growth, decreases negative behaviors and increases time spent academically engaged.

Mcfall (2023) believed that teachers who are entrusted with the role of educational affirm their commitment of excellence. Teacher's competence or efficiency is primarily adhered to his ability to manage classroom.

Similarly, Miranda (2023) in his study revealed that teachers are competent in the implementation of classroom routines particularly on managing learners and utilization of instructional facilities and materials in the course of teaching process hence, these classroom management competencies of teachers may contribute to increase meaningful learning.

Classroom Management is essential if learners are to learn effectively. Good managers are good leaders who are confident, positive and professionals and make good plans and understand the human behavior. Effective managers can involve learners in planning and helping with simple management tasks to encourage teamwork. When discipline is necessary for individual learners, it is done to help the learners and not for revenge as Cauley (2021) explains. It involves to total plan to address a variety of circumstances.

Evertson (2022) characterized classroom management as the actions taken to create an environment that the supports and facilitates academic and social-emotional learning. Toward this goal, teachers must (1) develop caring, supportive relationships with and among learners; (2) organize and implement instructions in order to optimize learners' access to learning; (3) the group management methods encourage learners' engagement in academic tasks; (4) promote the development of learners' social skills and self-regulation; and (5) use appropriate interventions to assist learners with behavior problems.

Garret (2022) also describes classroom management as a process consisting of key tasks that teachers must attend to in order to develop an environment conducive to learning. These tasks include organizing the physical environment, establishing rules and routines, developing caring relationships, engaging in an effective instruction and preventing and responding to discipline problems including the provision of a lively classroom environment.

Kauchak and Eggen (2023) explain classroom management in terms of time management. The goal of classroom management according to Kauchak and Eggen is not only to maintain order but to optimize learner learning. They provide class time into four overlapping categories namely; allocated time, instructional time, engaged time and academic learning time.

As pointed out by Good (2023), good classroom management is one of the strongest influences on academic learning. It is one of the main concerns of teachers, administrators and parents. It is one of the main concerns of teachers, administrators and parents. If the school is to live up to the community's expectations that it is a learning-producing enterprise, the individual classrooms which comprise the school must contribute to the schools' education productivity.

One of the most challenging and difficult functions of a teacher in classroom management had often been on the issue of dealing with individual learner behavior; also the ability of the teacher to control or manage the class as reflected in the quietness of learners. However, current thinking would emphasize management of the class as a means of establishing a routine that enables learning to move smoothly and prevent unnecessary discipline problems. Of course, from a pedagogical point, only in an orderly classroom can learning occur. Orderly does not mean quiet or rigid. An orderly classroom is one in which the teacher and every learner knows exactly what is going on. The success of teaching and learning depends to great extent on the way the class is organized and managed.

In the same manner, Stronge (2023) has cited some principles of classroom management which are also contributory to improve the teaching learning environment. These are as follows:

1. Consistent, proactive discipline is the crux of effective classroom management.

“Prevention is better than cure”, so goes the adage. If we are proactive in our approach to discipline we prevent unnecessary discipline problems to erupt for us to take a move. It is analogous to picking up a banana peeling when we see one scattered along the sidewalk, before anyone will slip and break his or her bones. We may pick up the banana peeling after the accident but it is quite late for damage has already been done. In short, let us anticipate potential problems and nip them in the bud.

To be consistent in our classroom management, we apply at all times established rules and policies to all learners/learners regardless of creed, color economics status, academic standing in class, we do not say this and do another. That will be a blow to our credibility.

2. Establish routines for all daily tasks and needs.

Routinized collection of assignments, passing of papers, and preparation for experiments saves as a lot of time and effort. We have not to explain or instructor learners/learners on how to pass papers, collect assignments, prepare for experiments day in and day out because we have established the routines for these everyday tasks. Learners/learners already know what to do and under what condition. Routine procedures give rise to orderly learning environment and maximum and optimum use of precious time. Doyle says, “routinization makes classroom activities less susceptible to breakdowns and interruptions because learners know the normal sequence of events and what is expected of them.”

3. Orchestrate smooth transitions and continuity of momentum throughout the day.

Smooth transitions and continuity on momentum throughout the day ensure us that every instructional moment is made use of wisely. No unnecessary lull created that will breed classroom restlessness, which is the father of disciplinary problems.

4. Strike a balance between variety and challenge in learners' activities. A variety of learner activities will ensure that learners' multiple intelligences and varied learning style are considered in the conduct of learner activities. Most of the time our activities fall under the linguistically intelligent group category. Games that require word use, talking, writing will certainly challenge that linguistically intelligent learners but bore the logic and math wizards and other groups of different intelligences. When boredom creeps into the classroom, we have disciplinary problems in our hands.

An extremely easy learning task does not challenge our learners and students. Neither does an extremely difficult one. It is the golden mean between the extremes of easy and difficult that will keep our learners/learners reasonably occupied.

5. As classroom manager, be aware of all actions and activities in the classroom. Our heightened awareness of everything that is happening in our classroom puts our learners and learners on their toes all the times. While our back faces them when we write on the board, our "eyes on the back of our heads" will make our learners and learners feel that we know what they are doing. Our visibility in and outside the classroom may serve as a deterrent in the outbreak of untoward learners' behavior. Research findings point that "effective classroom management skills include the use of space and proximity or movement around the classroom for nearness to trouble spots and to encourage attention."

6. Resolve minor inattention and disruption before they become major disruptions. The old adage "a stitch in time saves nine" aptly applies here. We have not to wait until our class is out of control. Misdemeanor has a "ripple effect" if not checked early. Conflagration begins with a spark. Put out at the spark early enough to avoid conflagration. We ought to respond to inappropriate behavior promptly.

7. Reinforce positive behavior. Be generous with genuine praise. Some teachers are quite stingy with praise. These are the teachers who think will become less when they praise others. They have to so-call "subtraction mentality." Other teachers are overgenerous with their praise. Their praises overflow so much that they give praise even when it is not appropriate. For our praise to be genuine it must be given according to merit. It is our way to appreciating and derecognizing hard work and good behavior.

8. Treat minor disturbance calmly. "Do not make a mountain out of a mole." If a stern look or gesture kills the inappropriate behavior so be it. That's the end period! Let us not make a fuss about it:

9. Work out physical arrangement of chairs that facilitates an interactive teaching-learning process. There is no doubt that external environment affects us. The most common arrangement of tables and chair in the classroom is one where the teachers' table and chairs are in front and the learner's desk or chairs are arranged in rows facing the teacher. This seat arrangement does not always enhance interaction among learners. Let us work for a flexible seating arrangement where we can re-arrange seats or desk to suit our learning needs and conditions.

Competencies Along Classroom Management

Paguyo (2023) stressed that the teacher must established and explain clearly to learners work assignments, feature of the work, standards to be met and procedures. According to him, explanations should be made in both oral and written form for instructions in assignments. In addition to telling the learners about assignments teacher should post assignments on the chalkboard or distribute duplicated copies and the learners in turn should be required to copy the assignments.

Kounin (2023) disclosed the importance of responding immediately to group learners' behavior that might be inappropriate or undesirable in order to prevent problems rather than having to deal with them after they emerge or come up. He describes this a the "ripple effects." In sum, Kounin believes that learner's engagement in lessons and activities is the key to successful classroom management. The successful teacher/classroom manager has a clear sense of direction and sequence for tasks. Smooth transitions are made from one activity to another and lessons are well paced namely;

Used structures curricula rather than discovery learning, emphasize small briskly paced instructional components, provide detailed and repetitious instructions and explanations, provide numerous examples, include frequent and immediate feedback and correction, design instruction for high rates of success, limit the duration of seatwork and arrange for over learning to occur through frequent drill and practice.

Likewise, Kounin (2023) pointed out that classroom activities can be analyzed for purposes of management. It may be divided into two categories-of purpose of management. It may be divided into two categories-of learners' behavior and teacher management behavior.

Kounin's further discussed the behaviors and categories for observing classroom management which included two major parts.

1. Work involvement. This is the amount of time learners spend in assigned academic task. Learners who are involved in works, e.g. answering assignments in workbook, reading a story reciting a poem or watching a demonstration lesson manifest or display lesser disciplinary problem than children who are not involved in any assigned learning task. It is basic in any learning situation that if the teacher keeps the learners busy in their work, there is less chance that boredom and discipline problems will arise;
2. Deviancy. From the sociological viewpoint is any act that violates social expectations, elicit social disapproval or non-conformity with the social norm. this ranges from simple misbehavior to serious behavior. Misbehavior occurs when the learner is not purposefully doing anything, but upsetting or annoying member of the class. Mild misbehavior includes actions life whispering, teasing, making faces. Reading a comic strip or passing notes. Serious misbehavior is manifested by aggressive or harmful behavior that virtually interferes with others or violates school rules. It is important not to allow mild misbehavior to generate into serious misbehavior by dealing with the mild misbehavior as soon as it occurs.

According to Borich (2020), the way groups accomplish the tasks and resolved concern determine the extent to which the teacher can effectively and efficiently manage and accomplish

goals of the classroom.

Schmuck (2022) believes that the sources of social power acquired by the teachers are important for guiding the learners through the process of group development. He believes that every successful group passes through the series of stage of development during which it has a certain task to accomplish and concern to resolve. He asserts that there is certain teaching behavior with overlapping and group focus that are related to managerial success. These focus that are related to managerial success. These techniques of classroom management apply to the classroom group not merely to the individual learner.

According to Acuro, (2023) a good school housekeeping is an important aspect of managing the environment. A school room that is neat, tidy, orderly and cheerful is made more inviting with a few plants, pictures, display of children's work, and other up-to-date informational materials.

The quality of the physical facilities may vary. The teachers should see to it that the room is artistically decorated, arranged and rearranged every now and then, easy to keep and learn better in an artistically satisfying environment.

An obvious sign of poor teaching is inability to set up the managerial procedure in the classroom. Unless the details of the classroom are systematically and carefully planned and implemented, much time will be lost, little will be accomplished, confusion may arise, and inefficiency result, hence, learning will suffer.

Managing Relationship

Classrooms management can be made more effective by building a humanistic classroom, based on learner rapport and understanding. In a humanistic classroom, teachers emphasize interpersonal relations and cooperative process.

Johnson (2022) identified three methods of developing a humanistic classroom, developing and maintaining trust, and communicating effectively.

Feedback tells learners what effect their actions are having on others. It is important for the teachers to provide feedback in a way that does not threaten the learner. To build a healthy relationship among the learners and between learners and teacher, a climate of mutual trust must grow and develop. All behaviors convey messages. Effective communication takes place when the receiver interprets the sender's messages in the way that way intended; effective communication enhances understanding and cooperation among individuals. Mutual trust enhances the possibility of effective communication.

Managing Learners

Robertson (2020) emphasized the organization and management of learners as they engage in academic work. A well-managed classroom that is free from disruptions, where learners behave in an orderly manner and are involved enthusiastically in learning, exist where teachers have a clear idea of the type of classroom conditions, learner's behavior and instructional activities they wish to produce.

Robertson also has divided organizing and managing work into three major categories: establishment and communication of work assignment, standards and procedures, monitoring learner work; and feedback to learners. The business-academic approach involves a high degree of “time on task” and “academic engaged time” for learners. The idea is that when learners are working on their tasks, there is little opportunity for discipline problems to arise. The teacher organized learners’ work, gives them tasks, monitor their work, gives them feedback, and holds them accountable by providing rewards and penalties. He stressed that an effective classroom manage incorporates eleven (11) managerial methods, all of which have been shown to correlate with improved learner achievement and behavior.

Readying the classroom. Classroom materials, space, materials and equipment are ready at the beginning of the year. Effective manager has better arranged their rooms, and they have coped more effectively with existing constraints, Planning rules and procedures. Teacher make sure learners understand and follow rules and procedures; they spend more time in the beginning of the year explaining and reminding learners of rules. Teaching rules and procedures. Rules and procedures are systematically taught and reinforced. Most of these teachers have taught their learners to respond to certain cues or signals, such as a bell of the teacher’s call for attention, Consequences for not following rules and procedures are clearly established by the teachers; there is consistent follow through, beginning of school activities. The first few days spend getting learners ready as a coherent and cooperative group. Once established, these teachers sustain a whole-group focus, Strategies for potential problems. Strategies for dealing with potential problems are planned in advance. With these strategies’ teachers can deal with misbehavior is closely monitored; the teacher does not lose audience contact; learners’ academic work is also monitored, Stopping inappropriate behavior. Inappropriate or disruptive behavior is handled promptly and consistently before it worsens or spreads, Organizing instruction. Teahce4rs organize instructional activities at suitable levels for all learners in the class. There is a high degree of learner success and content related to learner interests, learner’s accountability. Procedures have been developed for keeping learners for their work and behavior, Instructional clarity, teachers provide clear instructions; these helps keep learners in task and follow them to learn faster, while reducing discipline problems. Directions are clear; thus, confusion is minimized.

It is also considered a well-run classroom free from disruptions where learners behave in an orderly manner and are highly involved in learning. They exist where teachers have a clear idea of the type of classroom conditions, learner’s behavior and instructional activities they wish to produce.

Olsen, (2022) emphasizes the organization and management of the learners as they engage in the academic work. Task orientation, that is focusing on the business-like and orderly accomplishments of academic work leads to a clear set of procedures for the learners’ work into three major categories; establishment and communication of work assignments, standards and procedures, monitoring of learners’ work and feedback to learners.

Albuzo, (2023) asserted that good discipline comes from good teaching.

He stressed that discipline is an important factor in the development of character. It involved systematic training of the physical, moral and social capacities of the learner. Discipline

connotes control through obedience, orderly behavior and self-direction. For a school to function well, there is a need for discipline. In dealing with discipline in the high school, teachers and administrators must be prepared for the exigencies of changing conditions.

Disciplinary problems arise from disorderly behavior. Anent this, four general dimensions of disorderly behavior have been identified. These are as follows:

1. Hyperactivity. This is defined as high level of activity, non-aggressive conduct;
2. Inattentiveness. This is the inability to complete work and activities;
3. Conduct disorder. This is the inability to accept correction, tendency to tease others, high level of defense; and
4. Impulsivity. This is a constant demand for attention, present orientation, unpredictability.

To maintain effective classroom management, the teacher should be able to know the learners and the cause, of the learners' poor work and behavior. The teacher who has common sense, emotional maturity, and good professional training can translate the learner's inappropriate behavior into better efforts before such behavior becomes uncontrollable.

In maintaining effective discipline in the classroom, the following strategies are suggested:

Accept the learners as they are but build and accentuate their positive qualities, be yourself, be confident; don't give up in front of the learners, provide structure, Explain, rules and routine matter, communicate positive expectations, rely on motivation to maintain order, be a firm friend, keep calm and keep the learners calm, size up the situation, anticipate behavior, and except, but don't accept, misbehavior.

Many a time, these have been said of teachers: "He couldn't get discipline because he could not teach." "He could teach all right if he could only some discipline" or "He failed as a teacher not because he couldn't teach, but because he couldn't keep discipline."

According to Charles (2023) there are three (3) types of discipline. These are preventive, supportive and corrective. Although one may find that one category would be more suitable to personal teaching style than another, circumstances will often call for alternate disciplinary approaches. When developing one's own classroom management plan, it is important therefore, to carefully consider the appropriate role of each type.

Discipline is an integral part of classroom management and it often involves how teachers try to teach individual learners' better behavior. It is best conducted calmly. Learners are likely to be angry when called down and may require a cool down period. Teachers may need the same thing.

Soltis (2021) believed that one of the most difficult managerial tasks for the teacher is dealing with the hostile or aggressive group. Such a classroom group subtly and overtly defies the teacher and disrupts instructional activities. The symptoms that reveal this condition are: continual talking lack of attention when instructional tasks are presented constant disruptions that

interfere with teaching, over-all non-conformity to classroom rules and school practices, overt challenges and refusal to obey and group solidarity in resisting the teachers' efforts.

Beltran, (2023) pointed out that if the teachers do not diagnose group guidance problems, these will persist and increase. When such problems exist having group differences and identifying causes of conflicts.

Managing Resources

According to Jones (2023) good teaching requires a rich environment of instructional materials and devices. Instructional device and materials will challenge the attention of the learner stimulate thinking, the facilitate understanding which make learning more meaningful.

With the work systematized, the teacher can have more time for more creative tasks, record keeping, report making, remedial teaching, and guidance and counseling.

A well-managed classroom will give the learner opportunities for mental growth and development. Obviously, therefore, a teacher should be a diligent manager of physical environment as well as tactful manager of individual.

Zulueta (2022) pointed out that one character trait of an effective teacher is the ability to manage resources. These resources include the 3Ms moments, materials and man. On the other hand, in the context of teaching-learning, we have to consider also the three (3) elements which are time, teaching materials and the learners themselves.

Mcfall (2023) disclosed that teachers who entrusted with the role of education affirm their commitment of excellence. Teachers' competence of efficiency is primarily adhered to one's ability to manage classroom.

Classroom Management Approaches

Seven approaches to classroom management, which are grounded in research, have been identified by Ornstein. These are: acceptance approach, assertive approach, behavioral modification approach, business-academic approach, group-guidance approach, group-managerial approach and success approach.

Acceptance Approach

Acceptance approach is rooted in humanistic psychology and maintains that every person has a prime need for acceptance. Learners, like everyone else strive for acceptance. They want to belong and to be liked by others who are important to them more that they want to learn. Similarly, they would rather behave than misbehave. It is also based on the democratic model of teaching in which the teacher provides leadership by establishing rules and consequences, but at the same time allows learners to participate in decisions and make choices. One of its proponents is Stevenson (2021) who is noted for disciplinary approach on the need for acceptance. He maintains that acceptance by peers and the teachers are the prerequisites for appropriate behavior and achievement in school. People try all kinds of behavior to get status and recognition through socially acceptable methods, then they will turn to maintain to mistaken goals that result in antisocial behavior.

Acierto (2020) stated that the first thing that teachers need to do is to identify learner's mistaken goal. He stressed further that if the learners stop the behavior and then repeat it, their goal is getting attention; if the learners refuse to stop or increase their misbehavior, their goal is getting revenge; and if learners refuse to cooperate or participate, their goal is withdrawal. After teachers identify the mistaken goals, they need to confront the learners with an explanation of what they are doing. The dialogue should be done in a friendly, non-threatening manner.

Assertive Approach

Canter (2023) pointed out that under assertive approach, teacher must establish firm management right at the start. This denotes authoritarian leadership. The authoritarian leader wields absolute power over the subordinates. Authoritarian leadership is generally decisive and efficient. However, the group members generally respond out of necessity and not because of commitment to group goals.

This approach to classroom management expects the teacher to specify rules of behavior and consequences for disobeying them. These rules and consequences should be communicated clearly to the learners during the first day of classes. It is important that the learners know and realize that they should be held accountable for their actions. The teachers can devise his rules based on sound criteria of imposing sanctions for learners who misbehave. For learners who disobey rules for the first time, receive "one warning and, then, if they commit another infraction of the rules, they are subjected to an increasingly serious sanction."

It may be inferred that these techniques assume that firm classroom management liberated learners because it allows them to develop their best traits, skills and abilities and provides them with psychological security in the classroom and an effective learning environment. It may also be assumed that effective teachers usually handle discipline problem on their own way and that probably teaching failure is directly related to the inability to maintain adequate classroom discipline. This approach is perhaps most effective at the secondary level where chronic learner behavior problems normally exist.

There are a number of suggestions for teachers who would apply assertive discipline as an approach to classroom management. These are as follows; Clearly identify learning expectations, Take decisive positions (Say, "This is good" or "That is not good"), Use of firm (not soft or yielding) tone of voice, Employ eye contact and meaningful gestures to supplement verbal messages, Say no with our guilt feelings, Give and receive compliments spontaneously, Place demands and set limits on the learners and enforce them, Point out consequences of behavior and explain why specific action is necessary, Be calm and consistent; avoid display of emotion and threats, Establish positive expectations for learners behavior and try to eliminate negative expectations about learners and Gain confidence and management skills in identifying and working with chronic problems in the classroom.

It may be assumed that teachers who are able to apply assertive discipline technique not only have teaching confidence in their own abilities as teachers, but also get along better with learners.

According to Najera (2021), Assertive model holds the teachers most established firm management at the beginning of the year by (1) classifying appropriate expectations or

responsible behavior (2) identifying existing or potential discipline problems, (3) deciding on negative and positive consequences of behavior that fit the learners and situation and (4) learning follow through and implement these consequences.

Assertive Approach based on Almanza (2020) has a model of discipline in which teachers insist on responsible behavior of their learners. The teacher takes charge of the classroom immediately, sets the ground rules and interacts with learners in a calm yet forceful way.

Business-Academic Approach

According to Evertson (2023), business-academic approach emphasized the organization and management of learners as they engage in academic work. A well-managed classroom that is free from disruptions, where learners behave in an orderly manner and are involved enthusiastically in learning, exist where teachers have a clear idea of the type of classroom conditions, learner's behavior and instructional activities they wish to produce.

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follow them to learn faster, while reducing discipline problems. Directions are clear, thus confusion is minimized.

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Paguyo (2020) stressed that the teacher must establish and explain clearly to learners work assignments, feature of the work, standards to be met and procedures. According to him, explanations should be made in both oral and written form for instructions in assignments. In addition to telling the learners about assignments teacher should post assignments on the chalkboard or distribute duplicated copies and the learners in turn should be required to copy the assignments.

Behavior-Modification Approach

The behavioral-modification approach involves a variety of techniques and methods, using a system of rewards, punishments and reinforcement (Ornstein, 2023). This approach involves techniques and methods, that ranging from simple rewards to elaborate reinforcement training. He believed that behavior is shaped by the environment and pay little attentive to the causes of problems. Teachers utilizing approach spend little time on the personal brought about by a particular problem. Teachers strive to increase their involvement in the occurrence of appropriate behavior through as systematic and consistent system of giving rewards and to reduce the possibility of in appropriate behavior through punishment or penalty for misbehavior.

The basic principles of the behavioral modification approaches are as follows:

Learners achievement and behavior. These are:

Behavior is shaped by its consequences, not by the causes of problems in the history of the individual or by group conditions. Behavior is strengthened by immediate reinforces. Positive reinforces are praises or rewards. Negative reinforces take away or stop something that the learner does not like, Behavior is strengthened by systematic reinforcement. Behavior is weakened if not followed by reinforcement, Learners respond better to positive reinforces than they do to punishment, When a learner is not rewarded for appropriate or adaptive behavior, inappropriate or maladaptive behavior may become increasingly dominant and will be utilized to obtain reinforcement, Constant reinforcement – the reinforcement of a behavior every time it occurs-produces the best results, especially in new learning or conditioning situations, Once, the behavior has been learned, it is best maintained through intermittent reinforcement, Intermittent reinforcement schedules include (a) variable ration, (b) fixed ratio, and (c) fixed interval, There

are several types of reinforcers, each of which may be positive or aversive and rules are established and reinforced.

A well-known system utilized in the behavioral modification approach is modeling. Building good discipline through modeling includes.

Demonstration. Learners know exactly what is expected. In addition to having exerted behavior explained to them, they see and hear it, **Attention.** Learners focus their attention on what is being depicted, or explained. The degree of attention correlated, with the characteristics of the model (teacher) and characteristics of the learners, **Practice.** Learners are given the opportunity to practice the appropriate behavior, corrective feedback. Appropriate behavior is reinforced, inappropriate behavior is suppressed and corrected, and application. Learners are able to apply their learning in classroom activities.

Charles (2023) summarizes the teacher's role in modeling as follows:

Selects behavior to be learned, Selects most appropriate models, Sees that the behavior is modeled clearly, accurately and succinctly, Assists in helping observers focus attention on what is being modeled, Assists observers in remembering what they say, Provides for suitable practice in reenacting the observers in remembering what they saw, Provides for suitable practice in reenacting the observed behavior, Provides corrective feedback during learners reenactment and Provides reenactment following desired behaviors.

Behavioral-Modification Approach is rooted in the classic work of Watson and more recent work of Skinner. It involves a variety of techniques and methods ranging from simple to elaborate reinforcement trainings. Behaviorists assume the behavior is shaped by environment and pay little attention to the causes of problems.

Teachers using the behavioral-modification approach spend little time on the personal history of the learners or on searching for the reason of a particular problem. They strive to increase the occurrence of the appropriate behavior through a system of rewards and reduce the likelihood of the inappropriate behavior through punishment.

Group-Managerial Approach

Regarding the group-managerial approach, Kounin (2023) stressed the importance of responding immediately to group learner behavior that might be inappropriate or undesirable in order to prevent problems rather than having to deal with them after they emerge or come up. He describes this as the "ripple effect." In sum, Kounin believes that learners' engagement in lessons and activities is the key to successful classroom management. The successful teacher/classroom manager has a clear sense of direction and sequence for tasks. Smooth transitions are made from one activity to another and lessons are well paced namely;

Used structures curricula rather than discovery learning, Emphasize small briskly paced instructional components, Provide detailed and repetitious instructions and explanations, Provide numerous examples, Include frequent questions and opportunities to practice activity, Include frequent and immediate feedback and correction, Design instruction for high rates of success, Limit the duration of seatwork and Arrange for over learning to occur through frequent drill and

practice.

Likewise, Kounin pointed out that classroom activities can be analyzed for purposes of management. It may be divided into two categories-of learners behavior and teacher management behavior.

Kounin's behaviors and categories for observing classroom management include two major categories.

1. Work involvement. This is the amount of time learners spend in assigned academic task. Learners who are involved in work, e.g. answering assignments in workbook, reading a story reciting a poem or watching a demonstration lesson manifest or display lesser disciplinary problem than children who are not involved in any assigned learning task. It is basic in any learning situation that if the teacher keeps the learners busy in their work, there is less chance that boredom and discipline problems will arise;
2. Deviancy. From the sociological viewpoint, deviancy is any act that violates social expectations, elicit social disapproval or non-conformity with the social norm. this ranges from simple misbehavior to serious behavior. Misbehavior occurs when the learner is not purposefully doing anything, but upsetting or annoying member of the class. Mild misbehavior includes actins like whispering, teasing, making faces, reading a comic strip or passing notes. Serious misbehavior is manifested by aggressive or harmful behavior that virtually interferes with others or violates school rules. It is important not to allow mild misbehavior to generate into serious misbehavior by dealing with the mild misbehavior as soon as it occurs;

According to Borich (2020), the way groups accomplish the tasks and resolved concern determine the extent to which the teacher can effective and efficiently manage and accomplish the goals of the classroom.

Schmuck (2022) believes that the sources of social power acquired by the teacher are important for guiding the learners through the process of group development. He believes that every successful group passes through the series of stage of development during which it has a certain task to accomplish and concern to resolve. He asserts that there are certain teaching behaviors with overlapping and group focus that are related to managerial success. These focus that are related to managerial success. These techniques of classroom management apply to the classroom group not merely to the individual learners.

Group-Guidance Approach

The group guidance approach is based on the premise that since teachers have few opportunities to work with learners on an individual basis, they must learn to work with group of learners and to maintain group focus on the content and tasks of the group. Discipline and classroom control are produced through the group atmosphere and enhance through group rapport.

Peer tutoring is a technique used in the group guidance approach. In recent years, a great

deal of interest has been directed toward a program in which learners can coach or tutor one another. As a matter of fact, modern day research on peer tutoring shows that those who do the tutoring work learn more than those who are tutored.

Cooperative learning approach is akin to the group guidance approach. Grouping learners to work together instead of competing with each other is becoming a more accepted practice by teachers. In cooperative learning, learners divide the work among themselves, help one another, praise and criticize one another's efforts and contributions, and do peer tutoring among themselves.

Group-Guidance Approach is based on manipulating or changing the surface behavior of the learners on a group basis. Since the teachers have few opportunities to work with learners on an individual basis, they must learn to work with group of learners and to maintain group focus on the content and task of the group.

Seltis, (2021) believed that one of the most difficult managerial tasks for the teacher is dealing with the hostile or aggressive group. Such a classroom group subtly and overtly defies the teacher and disrupts instructional activities. The symptoms that reveal this condition are: continual talking lack of attention when instructional tasks are presented constant disruptions that interfere with teaching, over-all non-conformity to classroom rules and school practices, overt challenges and refusal to obey and group solidarity in resisting the teachers' efforts.

Beltran (2020) pointed out that if the teachers do not diagnose group guidance problems, these will persist and increase. When such problems exist having group differences and identifying causes of conflicts.

Success Approach

The success approach, otherwise known as the reality therapy, emphasizes the positive approach and it attractive to many educators. The approach hinges on helping, which is exactly what the teaching profession is about. This approach stresses that learners become more productive if what they do is psychologically satisfying, Glasser (2023). For instance, the school is changed not by changing the length of the school day or year of the amount of homework, but by making it more satisfying to learners and more consistent with their interests, so that they gain a sense of power, fulfillment and importance in the classroom. In her study, Bautista pointed out that although teachers should not tolerate bad behavior on the part of the learners, the teachers need to change whatever negative classroom conditions exists and improve conditions so that these will lead to learners' success.

Success Approach is rooted in humanistic psychological and the democratic model of teaching. However, instead of dealing with inappropriate behavior and the consequences of such behavior it deals with general psychological and social conditions.

Manalo (2020) insists that although teachers should not excuse had behavior on the part of the learners, they need to change whatever negative classroom conditions exists and improve conditions so they lead to learner success.

Effective Classroom Management

Effective classroom management has been described along the following dimensions: discipline, cooperative learning, social relationship, housekeeping, routine and physical environment.

Discipline

Regarding school discipline, Albuzo (2023) asserted that good discipline comes from good teaching.

He stressed that discipline is an important factor in the development of character. It involves systematic training of the physical, moral and social capacities of the learner. Discipline connotes control through obedience, orderly behavior and self-direction. For a school to function well, there is a need for discipline. In dealing with discipline in the high school, teachers and administrators must be prepared for the exigencies of changing conditions.

Disciplinary problems arise from disorderly behavior. These four general dimensions of disorderly behavior have been identified as follows:

1. Hyperactivity. This is defined as high level of activity, non-aggressive conduct;
2. Inattentiveness. This is the inability to complete work and activities;
3. Conduct disorder. This is the inability to accept correction, tendency to tease others, high level of defense; and
4. Impulsivity. This is a constant demand for attention, present orientation, unpredictability.

To maintain effective classroom management, the teacher should be able to know the learners and the cause, of the learners' poor work and behavior. The teacher who has common sense, emotional maturity, and good professional training can translate the learner's inappropriate behavior into better efforts before such behavior becomes uncontrollable.

In maintaining effective discipline in the classroom, the following strategies are suggested:

Accept the learners as they are but build and accentuate their positive qualities, Be yourself, Be confident; don't give up in front of the learners, Provide structure, Explain, rules and routine matter, Communicate positive expectations, Rely on motivation to maintain order, Be a firm friend, Keep calm and keep the learners calm, Size up the situation, Anticipate behavior, and Expert but don't accept, misbehavior.

Many a time, these have been said of teachers: "He couldn't get discipline because he could not teach." "He could teach all right if he could only set some discipline" or "He failed as a teacher not because he couldn't teach, but because he couldn't keep discipline."

According to Charles (2023) there are three (3) types of discipline. These are preventive, supportive and corrective. Although one may find that one category would be more suitable to personal teaching style than another, circumstances will often call for alternate disciplinary approaches. When developing one's own classroom management plan. It is important therefore,

to carefully consider the appropriate role of each type.

Discipline is an integral part of classroom management and it often involves how teachers try to teach individual learners' better behavior. It is best conducted calmly. Learners are likely to be angry when called down and may require a cool down period. Teachers may need the same thing.

Cooperative Learning

According to Collahan (2023), cooperative learning enables learners to learn how to work together, communicate effectively and to take responsibility for their own learning. Cooperative learning describes instructional procedures whereby learners work together and are rewarded for their accomplishments. Groups must be heterogeneous. Heterogeneity is fostered to improve the achievement of low-ability learners. Cooperative learning can be characterized by the kinds of tasks that are assigned to teams, by the rules of behavior required of team leaders, and by its unique system of rewards. Cooperative learning comes from in four (4) forms.

1. Learner Team Achievement Divisions (STAD). The STAD involves teachers' presentation, teamwork, quizzes, determination of scores, and team reward or recognition;
2. Teams, Games, Tournament (TGT). Involves teacher presentation, teamwork, team versus team competition, determination of scores and team reward;
3. Team-Assisted Individualization and Team-Accelerated Instruction (TAI). Combines the nature of cooperative learning. Team members check each other's work. Rewards based on the numbers of units of final test passed;
4. Cooperative Integrated Reading and Composition (CIRC). Mainly used to teach teaching and composition.

Cooperative Learning works well in a classroom climate that fosters wholesome, productive efforts shared by all members of the group. On the other hand, according to Schmucks (2023) positive classroom climate is created by teachers who stress the importance of group processes and skills develop through teamwork. A positive classroom climate is described as follows:

A positive social climate is one of which the learners expect one another to do their intellectual best and to support one another; where the learners share high amounts of potential influence both with one another and with the teachers; in which high levels of attraction exist for the young group as a whole and among classmates; where norms are supportive for getting academic work done, as well as for maximizing individual differences; where communication is open, featured by dialogue; and where the process of working and developing together as a group are considered relevant in themselves for study.

Social Relationship with Learners

Classrooms management can be made more effective by building a humanistic classroom, based on learners' rapport and understanding. In a humanistic classroom, teachers emphasize interpersonal relations and cooperative processes.

Johnson (2022) identified three methods of development a humanistic classroom, developing and maintain trust, and communicating effectively.

Feedback tells learners what effect their actions are having on others. It is important for the teacher to provide feedback in a way that does not threaten the learners.

To build a healthy relationship among learners and between learners and teacher, a climate of mutual trust must grow and develop.

All behaviors convey messages. Effective communication takes place when the receiver interprets the sender's messages in the way that was intended; effective communication enhances understanding and cooperation among individuals. Mutual trust enhances the possibility of effective communication.

On Housekeeping

A good school housekeeping is an important aspect of managing the environment. A schoolroom that is neat, tidy, orderly and cheerful is made more inviting with a few plants, pictures, display of children's work, and other up-to-date informational materials.

The quality of the physical facilities may vary. The teacher should see to it that the room is artistically decorated, arranged and rearranged every now and then, easy to keep, clean and well ventilated; has plenty of storage space. Children fell and learn better in an artistically satisfying environment.

An obvious sign of poor teaching is inability to set up the managerial procedure in the classroom. Unless the details of the classroom are systematically and carefully planned and implemented, much time will be lost, little will be accomplished, confusion may arise, and inefficiency results, hence, learning will suffer (Acuro, 2023).

On Routine

Routinizing activities can minimize the time and energy of learners and teachers. In can develop learner's initiative and can help them later with tem carry-over values in other situation in life.

On Physical Environment

According to Jones (2023) good teaching requires a rich environment of instructional materials and devices. Instructional device and materials will challenge the attention of the learner, and stimulate thinking, and facilitate understanding which make learning more meaningful.

With the work systematized, the teacher can have more time for more creative tasks, record keeping, report making, remedial teaching, and guidance and counseling.

A well-managed classroom will give the learning opportunities for mental growth and development. Obviously, therefore, a teacher be a diligent manager of physical environment as well as tactful manager of individual.

Biticon (2021) conducted a study on the variables affecting learner's achievement and

teacher's performance in multi-grade classes. Mcfall (2023) disclosed that teachers who entrusted with the role of education affirm their commitment of excellence. Teachers competence of efficiency.

Macario (2022) studied the problems of discipline encountered by the public elementary school teachers in the intermediate grades in San Nicolas District, Manila. She found out that discipline was a serious problem encountered. The disciplinary problems of the learners in the order of frequency were shyness, laziness, disorderliness, lack of cooperative and truancy. Shyness is a great problem of the girls.

Miranda (2023) investigated a study on classroom management competencies of Public Elementary School Teachers in the District II of Isabela, Negros Occidental. He found out that the elementary teachers are competent in the implementation of classroom routines particularly on managing learners, utilization of materials used in the course of the teaching process, making use of the facilities of the school, the proper filling of the school records and preparing school reports.

Algozzine (2023) made a study on the effect of School Home Parenting to Scholastic Performance of Intermediate Learners. He revealed that the most effective strategies for quickly addressing problem-behavior require attending to the learners who are cooperative and academically engaged.

Her findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between the School-Home Parenting to Scholastic Performance of Intermediate Learners.

Añonueva (2022) in her study on the role of elementary school teachers in classroom management revealed that teachers play an important role aside from home and the community. Teachers should maintain teaching positive values towards life and develop unique personalities. They are the ones who encourage learners to make their own decision in terms of the demands of the situation.

Parinque (2023) conducted a study on the classroom school teachers in classroom management competencies of Grade School Teachers in the Public and Private Schools in Lucena City: Basis for Teachers Development Program. Her findings revealed that teachers are highly competent in managing learning environment such as providing conducive learning and the maximum utilization of instructional materials.

Quetulio (2023) investigated a study on behavioral problems of learners in Tayug National High School. Her findings revealed that the three (3) factors which are parents, teacher and peer-related have been found to be significantly affecting the occurrence of the behavior problems. Her study disclosed that the teachers is an important reinforcing agent in the learner's life and developing positive relationship with learners is a vital commitment of the teacher.

Obispo (2023) conducted a study on Classroom Management Competencies of Secondary Teachers in Mayantoc, Tarlac. Findings revealed that secondary teachers are highly competent in dealing with the learners along establishing rules and procedures and in delegating functions and responsibilities to the learners.

Arellano (2022) conduct a study on classroom management approaches. His study disclosed that the successful teacher of today is an emotionally adjusted individual. He is conscious of the influence of his own personality upon his learners and adjusts his life in such a way that it will not affect them negatively. Her study further disclosed that the learners reflect his mood and disposition. If he displays a sense of human which is gay and vivacious likewise they are likely to be cheerful, helpful and responsive.

Martinez (2023) conducted a study on classroom management approach: Its Relation to the Discipline Practices of Public Elementary School Teachers in Calamba East District, Calamba City. Her study consisted of 150 teacher respondents.

Findings revealed that there is no significant difference between the two elementary schools with respect to discipline practices. Her study also disclosed that teacher has a big role in maintaining good classroom environment with well-disciplined learners, morally upright and academically excellent.

Mil (2023) conducted a study on classroom management competencies of secondary school teachers in the University of St. La Salle, Bacolod City. Findings revealed that the respondent teachers excelled most in managing social setting and classroom discipline likewise, they are also competent in physical setting and instructional planning.

Manangan (2023) conducted a study on Approached and Teachers' Effectiveness in Classroom Management in Palaris Colleges. Her respondents consisted of 228 and 28 school administrators.

Findings revealed that the teachers utilized the different classroom management approaches. Similarly, the teachers handled classroom management effectively in terms of discipline, cooperative learning, social relationships with learners, housekeeping, routine and physical environment. Further, the findings also revealed that there is a high positive correlation between the classroom management approaches and the level of effectiveness of the teachers' classroom management.

Reyes (2017) investigated a study on classroom management approaches of teachers in relation to their job performance. Findings showed that the extent to which teachers practice the different approaches to classroom management is described as often. Further. She found out that there is a high positive correlation between the extent to which the teachers practice the different classroom management approaches and their job performance. She also concluded that most of the teachers are not fully equipped with needed attainment and experiences to engage in classroom management.

Sanchez (2023) conducted a study on Classroom Management Competencies of Public Secondary School Teachers in SLSU, Lucban, Quezon. Findings revealed that teachers are highly competent on the basis of establishing rapport and flexibility with firmness. She also found out that teachers are democratic in their dealing with learners.

Ico (2023) conducted a study on Effective Classroom Management in Public Secondary Schools. She pointed out how the teachers solve the misbehavior of learner during class hours.

She found out that setting some rules and procedures in doing classroom routines and activities are effective in managing classroom. She also considered the importance of having seat plan for easy monitoring of learners' attendance and participation in class activities.

Valerio (2023) conducted a study on Best Classroom Management Practices of Grade 6 teachers in the Second District of Pangasinan. Her findings revealed that some of the best practices of teachers in classroom management are classroom discipline and establishing rules of conduct. The two (2) influence better performance of learners.

In view of this, the researcher has decided to conduct this study because she believed that classroom management is an integral part of teaching. And in order that a teacher can teach effectively, she must be able to possess the four (4) competencies of classroom management. It is perceived that ineffective classroom management is widely considered as one of the major educational problems. The classroom cannot function well without the teacher. Ultimately, the success of the teaching activities in the classroom depends to a great extent on the ability of the teacher as a classroom manager. In effect, this will contribute to improve the learning perspective of the learners.

Theoretical Framework

The study is also anchored on the theory of Behavioral-Modification by Ornstein (2021). This theory involves techniques and methods through giving of praises and rewards to elaborate reinforcement training.

In applying this theory, teachers should employ giving of praises, rewards including, recognition so as to strengthen their classroom management competencies particularly in matter of handling classroom learning environment and learners learning.

In applying this theory, teachers should employ giving of praises, rewards including, recognition so as to strengthen their classroom management competencies particular in matter of handling classroom learning environment and learners' learning.

The study was premised on Choice Theory of Sullo (2022). The choice theory is a biological theory that suggests we are born with specific needs that we are genetically instructed to satisfy. All of our behavior represents our best attempt at any moment to satisfy our basic needs like food, clothing, shelter and others. In additional to the physical need for survival, we have four basic psychological needs that must be satisfied namely: belonging or connecting, power or competence, freedom and fun.

In applying this theory, teachers should make sure that classroom endeavors are intended to satisfy learners' needs more likely, to be intrinsically motivated. This primarily allows to improve learning perspectives. Learners are able to have sense of belongings and freedom in a more conducive learning environment.

The study is likewise premised on the theory of social learning or observational learning. According to Bandura (1986), observational learning takes four steps: (1) paying attention and perceiving the most critical features of another person's behavior, (2) remembering the behavior (3) reproducing the action, (4) being motivated to learn and carry-out the behavior. Not all

behavior witnessed is learned or carried-out. Instead of learning occurring through trial and error, with successes being reinforced and failures punished, many important skills are learned through observation processes.

In applying this theory, teachers should consistently monitor learners' behavior while they are in classroom. They should regularly observe activities of learners whether they are in their right track or not. Further, they should be aware of their characteristics as one-vital ingredient of an effective classroom management.

Summing up these concepts and studies reviewed by the researcher provided rich background in improving classroom management competencies of teachers along the four (4) dimensions namely; Managing the Learning Environment, Managing Relationships, Managing Learners and Managing Resources.

Conceptual Framework

The schematic presentation of the study was illustrated in input-process-output model. The input consisted of level of classroom management competencies of teachers and their strengths and weaknesses.

The process consisted of the in-depth analysis of the level of classroom management competencies including their strengths and weaknesses. It also consisted of the formulation of a proposed action plan.

Finally, the output is a proposed action plan to enhance the competencies of teachers along classroom management.

Paradigm of the Study

Statement of the Problem

The study sought to determine the classroom management competencies of teachers in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) in the Public Senior High School of Anda, Division of Pangasinan I during the school year 2025-2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of classroom management competencies of teachers as perceived by themselves and their school administrators along:
 - a. Managing the Learning Environment,
 - b. Managing Relationship,
 - c. Managing Learners, and
 - d. Managing Resources?
2. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers themselves and their school administrators in the different dimensions of classroom management competencies?
3. What are the strengths and weaknesses of teachers in their classroom management competencies?
4. What proposed plan of action to be formulated to improve or enhance the Classroom Management competencies of teachers?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was tested at the .05 level of significance.

1. There are no significant differences between the perceptions of teachers themselves and their school administrators in the different dimensions of classroom management competencies.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study was delimited to the classroom management competence of senior high school teachers in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) of teachers along the four (4) dimensions namely; Managing the Learning Environment, Managing Relationships, Managing Learners and Managing during the school year 2025-2026.

Respondents consisted of a total enumeration of 94 Public Senior High School teachers and 5 school administrators of the five (5) public national high schools of Anda, Division of Pangasinan I.

Significance of the Study

The results of the study shall be projected to give research-based information and insights to the Curriculum Planners, School Administrators, Guidance Counselors, Teachers, Parents, Learners and the Researchers.

Curriculum Planners. They will profit from the study in terms of better way of planning the curriculum based on its findings relative to classroom management competencies of teachers.

School Administrators. The findings of the study can basically serve as bases for planning a staff development program focusing on classroom management. The findings of the study may also serve them as feedback regarding the level of competencies of teachers in managing classroom.

Guidance Counselors. The results of the study can benefit them by way of improving their school guidance and counseling program based from their analysis along teachers' level of competencies in classroom management. This may also serve for them as indication on the nature or kind of discipline learners have taken place.

Teachers. The findings of the study shall provide teachers a room for improvement in managing classroom thereby making teaching-learning process improve their moral fibers.

Learners. The results of the study can help them contribute to improve their academic performance and their national moralism out of the classroom management competencies of teachers.

Researcher himself shall benefit much not only in the conduct of the study but also in terms of the results of findings which can ultimately improve their level of competencies along classroom management.

Future Researchers shall benefit them by acquiring more insights and understanding on the efficacies of classroom management competencies.

Definition of Terms

In order to present a more thorough and comprehensive insights into this study, the following terms and phrases were defined lexically or operationally:

Basic Education. This refers to the elementary and secondary levels of the educational ladder.

Classroom Management. It refers to operation and control of activities involving details as seating arrangement, attendance, proper utilization of in traditional materials, classroom courtesies and discipline which require foresight and planning (Lardizabal, 2023)

Competency. It refers to the quality or state of being functionally adequate or of having sufficient knowledge, judgment, skill or strengths for a particular discipline (Webster, 1956)

Classroom Management Competencies. They refer to the four (4) dimensions of competencies in classroom management which are namely: Managing Learning Environment, Managing Relationships, Managing Learners and Managing Resources (Andrada, 2021).

Managing Learning Environment. It refers to a dimension of classroom management competency which is associated with conduciveness and setting up classroom environment based on learning needs and interest of learners.

Managing Relationship. It refers to establishing exemplary and concordant relationship

with the learners.

Managing Learners. It refers to the act or art controlling learners' behavior and other expectations and roles that emanate in the classroom.

Managing Classroom Resources. It refers to employing techniques and strategies for effective and efficient teaching-learning perspectives.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter presented the research design, respondents of the study, data-gathering instruments, data-gathering procedures and the statistical treatment of data which were utilized to analyze the data.

Research Design

The descriptive method was used in this study. This research method endeavors to describe systematically, factually, accurately and objectively a situation (Best, 2021). It sought to describe "what is". It was also suitable to situations which call for the analysis of differences without variable manipulation. Hence, the descriptive method is appropriate for the study.

The presented study primarily focused on determining the level of classroom management competencies along the identified four (4) dimensions. It further sought to determine the significance of the differences between the perceptions of the teachers themselves and their school administrators in their level of classroom management competencies of teachers.

Locale and Population of the Study

The study was conducted in the five (5) senior high schools in the municipality of Anda, Pangasinan during the school year 2025-2026. Respondents consisted of the total enumeration of 94 teachers and 5 school administrators.

Table 1 shown the distribution of respondents of the study by school.

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents by School

Schools	Senior High School Teachers	School Administrators
1. Anda National High School	23	1
2. Cabangang National High School	27	1
3. Carot National High School	24	1
4. Macaleeng National High School	10	1
5. San Jose National High School	10	1

TOTAL

94

5

Data-Gathering Instruments

The researcher study made use of the questionnaire as the main data-gathering instrument.

It consisted of the classroom management competencies along the four (4) dimensions namely; Managing the Learning Environment, Managing Relationships, Managing Learners and Managing Resources.

This is adopted from Andrada (2021), Department of Education Bureau of Secondary Education, Training Workshop on Productive Learning.

Data-Gathering Procedures

The researcher first sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent pertaining to the conduct of the study.

The set of questionnaires was personally floated by the researchers to the respondent teachers and the school administrators along the five (5) Public High Schools of Anda, Pangasinan. The administration of the said questionnaire lasted for three (3) weeks. Likewise, she personally retrieved all the questionnaire and the data were tallied, collated and presented in tables for analyses and interpretations.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Problem number 1 on determining the level of classroom management competencies of teachers was answered by using 5-Point Value Likert Scale with the average weighted mean (AWM) and their descriptive ratings as follows:

Scale	Descriptive Rating
5- (4.21-5.00)	Very Highly Competent (VHC)
4- (3.41-4.20)	Highly Competent (HC)
3- (2.61-3.40)	Moderately Competent (MC)
2- (1.81-2.60)	Fairly Competent (FC)
1- (1.00-1.80)	Poorly Competent (PC)

Problem number 2 on the significant differences between the perceptions of the teachers themselves and their school administrators in the different dimensions of classroom management competencies was answered by using the t-test.

Formula for t-test:

$$t = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{SD_{\bar{x}}}$$

Where:

\bar{X}_1 = first mean

\bar{X}_2 = second mean

$SD_{\bar{x}}$ = standard error of difference between the two means

$$SD_{\bar{x}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum \bar{X}_1^2 + \sum \bar{X}_2^2}{(N_1 + N_2) - 2} \left[\frac{1}{N_1} + \frac{1}{N_2} \right]}$$

Problem number 3 on determining the strengths and weakness of teachers along the dimensions of classroom management competencies was answered by using the mean scale value. A mean value of 3.41 and Above is classified as “Strength” while a mean value of 3.40 and Below is considered “Weakness”.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

This chapter presented, analyzed and interpreted the data gathered on the light of the problem posed in the study.

Table 2 dealt with the data on the level of classroom management competencies along Managing the Learning Environment.

Table 2

**Level of Classroom Management Competencies
Along Managing the Learning Environment**

A. MANAGING THE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT	Teachers		School		Overall	
	(N=94)		(N=5)			
	AWM	DR	AWM	DR	AWM	DR
1. Ensuring a conducive learning environment.	3.53	HC	3.74	HC	3.64	HC
2. Setting up nurturing environment based on learning needs of learners.	3.57	HC	3.55	HC	3.56	HC
3. Transforming a drab-looking classroom into a lively one.	3.32	MC	3.23	MC	3.28	MC
4. Converting a threatening classroom into a fun-filled	3.48	HC	3.34	HC	3.41	HC

learning environment.

OVERALL AWM 3.48 HC 3.46 HC 3.47 HC

Table 2 revealed the perceptions of the two (2) groups of respondents along the four (4) indicators of managing the learning environment which have average weighted mean range from 3.28 to 3.64.

The top three (3) indicators are: Ensuring a conducive learning environment (3.64). this means that the teachers are fully aware of the efficacies of a well-functional classroom. Such that a well-functional classroom also requires ventilation and good lighting asides from strong desks/armchairs including a sound and healthy personality corner. This indicated that a conducive learning environment/functional classroom can contribute to improve the level of teachers' classroom competencies.

Converting a threatening classroom in a fun-filled learning environment (3.41). it is described as highly competent. This means that the teachers are exercising democratize practices inside the classroom. The way they approach the treat their class are somewhat evident. This only showed that the teachers have full knowledge about management of learning perspectives. Setting up nurturing environment based on learning need of learners (3.56). This further meant that the teachers were highly observed the pressing learning needs in their respective schools. This showed that the senior high teachers basically consider the needs of learners in order for them to learn judiciously and effectively as well.

However, the lowest indicator which was Transforming a drab-looking classroom into a lively one (3.28) is described as moderately competent. This means that the teachers are not conscious of the efficacy of a lively classroom. This shows that the teachers lack motivation in their management of learning environment. Extrinsic motivation was very important ingredient in the teaching-learning process. This is in order to increase their level intrinsically. Providing learners such extrinsic motivation can help improve their learning environment.

Taken as a whole, the average weighted mean is 3.47 which is described as high extent. This implies that the teachers have the full knowledge on how to manage the learning environment.

Garret (2022) stressed out classroom management as a process of key tasks that teachers must acquire in order to develop an environment which is conducive to learning. These tasks include organizing the physical environment, engaging in an effective instruction, preventing and responding to discipline problems including the provision of a lively classroom environment.

Managing Relationships

Data on the level of classroom competencies along managing relationships were present in table 3.

Table 3 showed the ratings of the two (2) groups of respondents in the level of classroom competencies along Managing Relationships.

Table 3
Level of Classroom Management Competencies
Along Managing Relationships

B. MANAGING RELATIONSHIP	Teachers		School		Overall	
	(N=94)		(N=5)			
	AWM	DR	AWM	DR	AWM	DR
INDICATORS						
1. Establishing authority without being authoritarian.	3.47	HC	3.47	HC	3.47	HC
2. Delegating functions and responsibilities appropriate to varying need of learners.	3.25	MC	3.26	MC	3.26	MC
3. Strategizing on how to deal with unwanted behaviors.	3.35	MC	3.37	MC	3.36	MC
4. Preventing unwanted behaviors.	3.22	MC	3.26	MC	3.23	MC
5. Establishing rapport.	3.74	HC	3.68	HC	3.71	HC
6. Forging solidarity.	3.52	HC	3.41	HC	3.47	HC
7. Indigenizing (based) on the accepted norms in a certain locality.	3.77	HC	3.64	HC	3.70	HC
OVERALL AWM	3.47	HC	3.44	HC	3.45	HC

It is evident in the table that out of the 7 indicators, four (4) are described as highly competent and three (3) are moderately competent. Their average weighted means range from 3.23 to 3.71.

The top two (2) indicators are: Establishing rapport (3.71) which is described as highly competent. This means that the teachers are fully aware of the significance of interpersonal relationships with the class by being approachable and accommodating as vital needs of an effective classroom environment. This indicated that the teacher has the knowledge of dealing with learners harmoniously in terms of their ways and manner on how to dealt with them.

This has not to be underestimated in the sense that providing good rapport is necessary to ensure a sound and healthy classroom environment. Indigenizing (based) on the accepted norms in a certain locality has an average weighted mean of 3.71 which is described as highly competent. This means that the teachers have full knowledge of typical or widespread practices

and procedures which are really acceptable ones. This indicates that these sets of standards are apparently contributory to concordant relationships hence, one vital need of classroom management competencies of teachers.

However, on the other hand, the lowest two (2) indicators were: Preventing undated behavior (3.23). This means that the teachers lack ability to move steadily and gradually a unity in the classroom based on shared interest, objectives or standards. This indicator that the teachers are not conscious of the needs and interest of the class. They are only after for their own dispositions and set of classroom standards without letting class to participate in. this should be highly regarded in order for them to increase their level of classroom management competencies. Delegating functions and responsibilities appropriate to varying needs of learners (3.26) which is also described as moderately competent. This means that the teachers are not aware of the importance of delegating tasks or activities which are within the parameter needs of the learners like assigning them as group leaders to report the daily attendance in the classroom. Likewise, assigning some of them especially those brighter ones to help in checking the test papers and other relevant activities or tasks. This is not to be disregarded if not, we are impeding them nurture and develop their leadership training which is also considered as their vital need in the classroom.

Taken as a whole, the average weighted mean is 3.45 which is described as highly competent. This implies that teachers have the “know-how” on how manage relationships.

Johnson (2022) pointed out that classroom can be more effective by building a humanistic classroom, based on the learner rapport and understanding. In a humanistic classroom, teachers emphasize interpersonal relations and cooperative processes.

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Along Managing Relationships

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	(N=94)		(N=5)			
	AWM	DR	AWM	DR	AWM	DR
INDICATORS						
1. Establishing authority without being authoritarian.	3.47	HC	3.47	HC	3.47	HC

2. Delegating functions and responsibilities appropriate to varying need of learners.	3.25	MC	3.26	MC	3.26	MC
3. Strategizing on how to deal with unwanted behaviors.	3.35	MC	3.37	MC	3.36	MC
4. Preventing unwanted behaviors.	3.22	MC	3.26	MC	3.23	MC
5. Establishing rapport.	3.74	HC	3.68	HC	3.71	HC
6. Forging solidarity.	3.52	HC	3.41	HC	3.47	HC
7. Indigenizing (based) on the accepted norms in a certain locality.	3.77	HC	3.64	HC	3.70	HC
OVERALL AWM	3.47	HC	3.44	HC	3.45	HC

It is evident in the table that out of the 7 indicators, four (4) are described as highly competent and three (3) are moderately competent. Their average weighted means range from 3.23 to 3.71.

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Taken as a whole, the average weighted mean is 3.45 which is described as highly competent. This implies that teachers have the “know-how” on how manage relationships.

Johnson (2022) pointed out that classroom can be more effective by building a humanistic classroom, based on the learner rapport and understanding. In a humanistic classroom, teachers emphasize interpersonal relations and cooperative processes.

Managing Learners

Table 4 revealed data on the level of classroom competencies of teachers along managing learners.

Data in the table shown five (5) indicators where average weighted mean range from 3.30 to 3.70.

The top two (2) indicators were Defining expectations and roles of everyone in the classroom (3.70). this means that teachers are fully aware of what are supposed to consider in managing classroom with learners on the basis assigning them functions and other activities which are within their access and capabilities. This goes to show that teachers have fully knowledge of learners’ needs and interest so to provide sound intrinsic motivation hence, learners can perform activities better.

Table 4
Level of Classroom Management Competencies
Along Managing Learners

C. MANAGING LEARNERS	Teachers		School		Overall	
	(N=94)		(N=5)			
	AWM	DR	AWM	DR	AWM	DR
1. Defining expectations and roles of everyone in the classroom.	3.68	HC	3.72	HC	3.70	HC
2. Dealing with learners in a reciprocating manner.	3.65	HC	3.42	HC	3.54	HC
3. Respecting individual nuances or peculiarities.	3.38	MC	3.35	MC	3.36	MC

4. Bridging gaps in a constructive manner.	3.28	MC	3.31	MC	3.30	MC
5. Establishing rules and procedures through a positive and non-threatening approach (defining limits).	3.58	HC	3.72	HC	3.65	HC
OVERALL AWM	3.51	HC	3.50	HC	3.50	HC

Establishing rules and procedures through a positive and non-threatening approach (3.65). It only meant that teachers were fully conscious of the efficacy of classroom rules and procedures in a more viable and convincing manner. Such rules include the likes and dislikes of teachers and other policies which are within the flow of democratic perspectives. This indicated that teachers can allow learners develop them with such order and effective learning environment.

On the other hand, bridging gap in a constructive manner (3.30) which is described as moderately competent. This means that teachers do not have full perceptions in respect to the significance of more positive way or approach in dealing with learners.

They should be optimistic as regard to how classroom activities are organized and initiated. This further indicates that teachers may affect their classroom management competencies along this situation. Respecting individual nuances or peculiarities (3.36) is also described as moderately competent. This shows that teachers are not conscious of individual different of learners. This goes to show that teachers lack knowledge on the essence of how learners learn based on their needs and interest for an effective classroom perspective. This indicates that teachers may affect their competence related to classroom management. Hence, this should not be tolerated if not, it may bring less impact on learners' learning environment.

In general, the overall average weighted mean is 3.50 which is described as highly competent. This implies that teachers have the full knowledge in respect to managing learners in the classroom.

According to Evertson, (2023), disclosure was essential for the organization and management of learners as they engage in academic work was sometimes vital. He also believed that a well-manage learners in the classroom which is free from disruptions can bring learners in an orderly manner.

Managing Resources

Data on the level of classroom competencies of teachers along Managing Resources are present in table 5.

Table 5
Level of Classroom Management Competencies
Along Managing Resources

D. MANAGING RESOURCES	Teachers		School Administrators		Overall	
	(N=94)		(N=5)			
	AWM	DR	AWM	DR	AWM	DR
INDICATORS						
1. Employing techniques and strategies for effective and efficient teaching.	3.60	HC	3.74	HC	3.67	HC
2. Designing tasks to be carried out based on the allotted time.	3.15	MC	3.24	MC	3.20	MC
3. Highlighting teaching practices that are time and resource-based.	3.57	HC	3.58	HC	3.58	HC
4. Formulate schemes on how resources shall be used maximally.	3.78	HC	3.66	HC	3.72	HC
OVERALL AWM	3.53	HC	3.56	HC	3.55	HC

Table 5 reveals the perceptions of the two (2) groups of respondents in the four (4) indicators of managing resources out of the four (4) indicators, one (1) is moderately competent and three (3) are highly competent. Their average weighted mean ranges from 3.20 to 3.72.

The indicators which are described as highly competent were Formulate schemes on how resources shall be used maximally (3.72). This means that teachers are aware of regular utilization of resources in order to optimize learning environment. This indicates that teachers have full knowledge on how resources are managed like time element instructional technologies both modern and traditional ones.

Furthermore, teachers select and utilize resources based from the objectives of the lesson. In other words, teachers are conscious of the relevant, coherent and appropriate resources based from the learning competencies in order to cater its significance. Employing techniques and strategies for effective and efficient teaching (3.67). This means that teachers have the sufficient knowledge in using techniques and strategies in the attainment of successful teaching manifestations. This goes to show that they are aware of the method and manner in developing lesson like questioning technique, concept organization, and other relevant teaching activities. Highlighting teaching practices that are time and resource-based (3.58). This means that teachers

are well-adept in time management.

Proper management of time is one vital ingredient of a prolific teaching. This indicates, that teacher give more regards to efficacies of resources to make teaching more effective.

However, on the other hand, the fourth indicator Designing tasks to be carried out based on the allotted time (3.20) which is described as moderately competent. This means that teachers are less aware of the designated time or schedule of their subject being taught. This shows that they are not following exactly their class schedules as embodied in the class program. This has not to be tolerated for an effect, it may affect such prescribed time in the next learning area.

Taken as a whole, the overall average weighted mean is (3.55) which is described as highly competent. This basically implies that teachers have full knowledge in respect to managing resources a one dimension of classroom management competency.

Jones (2023) pointed out that good teaching requires a rich environment of instructional materials and devices. Instructional resources will challenge the attention of the learner, stimulate thinking and facilitate understanding which can make learning more meaningful.

Summary on the Level of Classroom Management Competencies of Teachers as Perceived by Themselves and Their School Administrators

Table 6 presented summary on the level of classroom management competencies of teachers along the four (4) dimensions.

Data in table 6 revealed that all the four (4) dimensions of classroom management competencies are described as highly competent. Their average weighted means range from 3.45 to 3.55.

These indicators were found to have average weighted mean accordingly. Thus, Managing the Learning Environment (3.54), Managing Resources (3.55), Managing Learners (3.50), Managing the Learning Environment (3.47) and Managing Relationship (3.45). The grand mean of the two (2) groups of respondents 3.50 which is described as highly competent.

Table 6
Summary on the Level of Classroom Management
Competencies in the Different Dimensions

Dimensions	Teachers		School Administrators		Overall	
	(N=94)		(N=5)			
1. Managing the Learning Environment	3.48	HC	3.46	HC	3.47	HC
2. Managing Relationships	3.47	HC	3.44	HC	3.45	HC
3. Managing Learners	3.51	HC	3.50	HC	3.50	HC
4. Managing Resources	3.53	HC	3.56	HC	3.55	HC
Total Average Mean	3.50	HC	3.49	HC	3.50	HC

Further scrutiny of the data reveals that the teachers possess the necessary knowledge and skills in managing classroom. Generally, this indicates that teachers have acquired the desired level of classroom management competencies.

Differences Between the Perceptions of Teachers and Their School Administrators in Their Level of Classroom Management Competencies Along the Four (4) Dimensions.

Table 7 revealed data on the perceptions of teachers and their school administrators along the four (4) dimensions of classroom management competencies.

Data in the table showed that the computer t-value and the critical value are 0.33 and 2.447 respectively.

Table 7
Differences Between the Perceptions of Teachers and them
School Administrators in the Different Dimensions of
Classroom Management Competencies

Dimensions	Teachers (N=94)		School Administrators DR(N=5)	
	AWM	DR	AWM	DR
	1. Managing the Learning Environment	3.48	HC	3.46
2. Managing Relationships	3.47	HC	3.44	HC
3. Managing Learners	3.51	HC	3.50	HC
4. Managing Resources	3.53	HC	3.56	HC
Total Average Mean	3.50	HC	3.49	HC

Computed t-value: 0.33

Alpha = .05

Critical Value: 2.45

Decision: Accept the Null Hypothesis

Interpretation: No Significant Difference

Close scrutiny of the data shown that the compute t-value is lesser than the critical value. This meant that the null hypothesis was accepted hence, there was no significant difference between the perceptions of the two (2) groups of respondents. Further, this computed t-values may be inferred that their perceptions did not vary and in the same footing.

Strengths and Weaknesses of Teachers Along the Four (4) Dimensions of Classroom Management Competencies

The strengths and weaknesses of teachers based on the criteria adopted were shown in the tablets that follow:

Strengths and Weaknesses of Teachers in the Level of Classroom Management Competencies along the Managing the Learning Environment

Table 8 revealed data on strengths and weaknesses of teachers along Managing the Learning Environment.

Table 8
Strengths and Weaknesses of Teachers Along
Managing the Learning Environment

Dimensions	Strengths	Weaknesses
A. MANAGING THE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT		
INDICATORS		
1. Ensuring a conducive learning environment	3.64	
2. Setting up nurturing environment based on learning needs of learners.	3.56	
3. Transforming a drab-looking classroom into a lively one.		3.28
4. Converting a threatening classroom into a fun-filled learning environment.	3.41	

It is apparent in table 8 that there were more strengths (3) than weaknesses (1) along the dimension of managing the learning environment. The strengths are found in activities relative to conduciveness of learning environment, setting up nurturing environment and sound learning perspectives.

Their weakness on the other hand were found in activities relative to establishing a lively and appreciative learning environment.

Strengths and Weaknesses of Teachers in the Level of Classroom Management Competencies Along Managing Relationships

Table 9 showed data on the strengths and weaknesses of teachers long Managing Relationships.

Table 9
Strengths and Weaknesses of Teachers Along
Managing Relationships

Dimensions	Strengths	Weaknesses
B. MANAGING RELATIONSHIP		
INDICATORS		
1. Establishing authority without being authoritarian.	3.46	
2. Delegating functions and responsibilities appropriate to varying needs of learners.		3.26
3. Strategizing on how to deal with unwanted behaviors.		3.36
4. Preventing unwanted behaviors.		3.23
5. Establishing rapport.	3.71	
6. Forging solidarity.	3.47	
7. Indigenizing (based on the accepted norms in a certain locality).	3.70	

Table 9 revealed that there are more strengths (4) than weaknesses (3) along the dimension of Managing Relationships. The weaknesses were activities associated with establishing authority without being authoritarian, providing solidarity and consistent rapport and teachers' actions based on standards.

However, their weaknesses were evidently anchored on the principals of delegation of functions and impeding from unnecessary class behaviors.

Strengths and Weaknesses of Teachers Along Managing Learners

Table 10 revealed data on strengths and weaknesses of teachers in the level of classroom management competencies along Managing Learners.

Table 10
Strengths and Weaknesses of Teachers
Along Managing Learners

Dimensions	Strengths	Weaknesses
C. MANAGING LEARNERS		
INDICATORS		
1. Defining expectations and roles of everyone in the classroom.	3.70	
2. Dealing with learners in a reciprocating manner.	3.54	
3. Respecting individual nuances or peculiarities.		3.36
4. Bridging gaps in a constructive manner.		3.30
5. Establishing rules and procedures through a positive and non-threatening approach (defining limits).	3.65	

It is evident in table 10 that out of the five (5) indicators of managing learners three (3) were classified as strengths and two (2) are considered weaknesses.

The strengths were areas relative to defining expectations and roles, interacting with learners using positive approaches and setting up rules and procedures in the classroom.

However, on the other hand, the weaknesses were activities associated with respecting learner's distinct characteristics including bridging gap in an inspiring manner.

Strengths and Weaknesses of Teachers Along Managing Resources

Table 11 revealed data on strengths and weaknesses of teachers in the level of classroom management competencies along Managing Resources.

Table 11

Strengths and Weaknesses of Teachers

Along Managing Resources

Dimensions	Strengths	Weaknesses
D. MANAGING RESOURCES		
INDICATORS		
1. Employing techniques and strategies for effective and efficient teaching.	3.67	
2. Designing tasks to be carried out based on the allotted time.		3.20
3. Highlighting teaching practices that are time and resource-based.	3.58	
4. Formulate schemes on how resources shall be used maximally.	3.72	

Data in table 11 revealed that out of the four (4) dimensions of Managing Resources, three (3) are categorized as strengths and one (1) is classified as weaknesses.

The strengths were areas associated with techniques and strategies for exemplary learning, time management inclusion maximization of relevant resources. On the other hand, the only weakness on the task-designing respective of the time allotment. This only implied that senior high school teachers employed suitable teaching techniques and strategies for effective and efficient training, however, did not excel in designing tasks to be carried out based on the allotted time because of overlapping of activities and abrupt suspension of classes due to some forces of nature such as typhoon and flooding in the area.

Proposed Action Plan to Enhance the Classroom Management Competencies of Teachers in the Municipality of Anda, Division of Pangasinan I

The action plan is primarily designed to improve the classroom management competencies of teachers based on the findings along the level of competencies relative to classroom management of teachers including their strengths and weaknesses.

The proposed action plan has the following components:

1. Areas of Concern
2. Objectives/Targets
3. Activities/Strategies
4. Person/Agencies Involved

5. Budget Estimate
6. Time Frame
7. Success Indicators

This is presented in matrix form found in the pages that follow.

**PROPOSED ACTION PLAN TO ENHANCE CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT
COMPETENCIES OF TEACHERS**

IN ANDA, DIVISION OF PANGASINAN I

Areas of Concern	Objectives /Targets	Activities/ Strategies	Persons/ Agencies Involved	Budget Estimate	Time Frame	Success Indicator
I. LEVEL OF CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES						
A. Managing the Learning Environment						
1. Transforming a monotonous classroom into a lively one.	To maximize class to work within their needs, interest and experiences.	a.) Through giving of appropriate motivation, class recitation, question and answer, development of the lesson, seatwork and homework.	Teachers Students	As needed	Year Round	90% of the teachers shall have maximized class to work within their needs, interests and experiences in teaching.
2. Setting up to positive learning environment.	To set up teachers sound and healthy learning environment.	a.) Through the use of democratic practices. b. Attending lecture and forum relative to provision of sound learning environment.	Teachers	As needed	Year Round	90% of the teachers shall have set up themselves sound and healthy learning environment.

c.) Modeling

3. Setting up well-nurtured environment.	To promote well-nurtured environment based on the needs of students	-Attend lecture and seminar relative to teaching principles and strategies where to address students needs. -Identify the learning styles of students. -Use of interview	Teachers School Administrators	As needed	Year Round	90% of the teachers shall have promoted a well-nourished environment based on the needs of students.
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Areas of Concern	Objectives /Targets	Activities/ Strategies	Persons/ Agencies Involved	Budget Estimate	Time Frame	Success Indicator
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B. Managing Relationships

1. Preventing Unwanted Behaviors.	Equip from impeding unnecessary behaviors of students.	-Maximization of students' participation in group work along cooperative and collaborative learning. -Giving students more responsibilities in the classroom that are within their interest and experiences.	Teachers Students	As Needed	Year Round	90% of the teachers shall have prevented unwanted behaviors of students in the classroom.
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2. Delegation of functions and responsibilities.	Maximize giving of students' tasks and responsibilities to perform in the classroom.	Assigning the some activities in the classroom like checker of daily attendance, as group leader, in-charge of maintaining discipline, group to monitor the upkeep of the classroom, etc.	Teachers Students	As Needed	Year Round	95% of the teachers shall have maximized giving of students tasks and responsibilities to perform in the classroom.
3. Strategizing on how to deal with unwanted behaviors.	To provide appropriate strategies on dealing with unwanted behavior of students.	-Maximize the parent-teacher partnership -Use of interview, dialogue -Close supervision and monitoring of the students with inappropriate behavior.	Teachers Parents Students	As Needed	Year Round	90% of the teachers shall have provided appropriate strategies relative to unwanted behaviors of students.

Areas of Concern	Objectives /Targets	Activities/ Strategies	Persons/ Agencies Involved	Budget Estimate	Time Frame	Success Indicator
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C. Managing Students

1. Bridging gaps in constructive manner.	Equip teachers utilize positive approach in dealing with	-Modeling -Attend lecture and seminar relative to sound management of students/students.	Teacher School Administrators	As Needed	Semestral Break	90% of the teachers shall have equipped themselves using positive
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students.

approaches
in dealing
with
students.

2.	Equip teachers from respecting students' peculiarities	-Identify one's strengths and weaknesses. -Modeling -Observation -Giving of students' activities that are within their needs, interest and aspirations.	Teacher	As Needed	Year Round	85% of the teachers shall have equipped themselves from respecting students' peculiarities.
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III. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presented the summary of significant findings, conclusions generated from the findings and recommendations made based on the findings and conclusions.

Summary

This study aimed to determine the classroom management competencies of teachers in the municipality of Anda, Division of Pangasinan I during the school year 2025-2026 in terms of their level of classroom management competencies including their strengths and weaknesses along the four (4) dimensions.

Respondents consisted of a total enumeration of 94 Public Senior High School Teachers and 5 School Administrators of Anda, Pangasinan.

Findings

The salient findings of the study were as follows:

1. The level of classroom management competencies of teachers along the four (4) such as Managing the Learning Environment (3.54), Managing Resources (3.55), Managing Learners (3.50), Managing the Learning Environment (3.47) and Managing Relationship (3.45). These dimensions were described as highly competent proven by the weighted average mean of (3.50).

2. There were no significant differences between the perceptions of teachers themselves and their school administrators in their level of classroom management competencies in the different dimensions.
3. There were more strengths of teachers than weaknesses in all the dimensions of classroom management competencies.
4. An action plan was formulated to enhance the classroom management competencies of senior high school teachers in Anda, Pangasinan.

Conclusions

Based on findings of the study the following conclusions were drawn:

1. It was revealed that senior high school teachers in Anda, Pangasinan demonstrate a **high level of classroom management competencies** across all identified dimensions, including managing the learning environment, resources, learners, and relationships. The overall weighted mean indicates that teachers are generally **highly competent** in effectively handling classroom dynamics;
2. Moreover, the findings showed that there was **no significant difference** between the self-assessment of teachers and the evaluations made by their school administrators, suggesting a strong alignment in perceptions regarding teachers' competencies. This consistency reflects an accurate and reliable assessment of classroom management practices;
3. Meanwhile, results on the gathered data where senior high school teachers possess **more strengths than weaknesses** in all dimensions, reinforcing their capability to maintain effective and productive learning environments;
4. Finally, the development of an action plan signifies a proactive approach toward **continuous improvement**, ensuring that teaching practices remain responsive to evolving educational needs of the senior high school learners.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were hereby forwarded:

1. Schools should continue supporting teachers through regular training, workshops, and seminars focused on enhancing classroom management skills to maintain their high level of competence;
2. The proposed action plan should be fully implemented and regularly monitored to ensure its effectiveness in further improving teachers' competencies;
3. Encourage peer mentoring, coaching, and sharing of best practices among teachers to further strengthen their classroom management strategies;

4. Conduct periodic evaluations involving both teachers and administrators to maintain alignment in perceptions and to identify areas for improvement and address minor weaknesses. Although strengths outweigh weaknesses, targeted interventions should be designed to address specific areas needing improvement for more balanced competency development.

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